

Optimizing and Predicting Traffic Flow on Mantagbac Bridge: A Microscopic Simulation Approach

Emil J. Dar
College of Computing and Multimedia
Studies
Camarines Norte State College
Paracale, Philippines
emildar134@gmail.com

Christina G. Seña
College of Computing and Multimedia
Studies
Camarines Norte State College
Vinzons, Philippines
christina.sena01@gmail.com

Hannah Fiona O. Cereno
College of Computing and Multimedia
Studies
Camarines Norte State College
Labo, Philippines
cerenohannahfiona@gmail.com

Vergel B. Villaranda
College of Computing and Multimedia
Studies
Camarines Norte State College
Mercedes, Philippines
vergelvillaranda0911@gmail.com

Princess Jyssa Sena
College of Computing and Multimedia
Studies
Camarines Norte State College
Talisay, Philippines
pjdsena@gmail.com

Abstract— This research attempts to solve the problem of traffic congestion at Bridge 3 Daet, Camarines Norte due to the constantly expanding percent of vehicles and poor traffic control. In proposing the development of a microscopic simulation model with VISSIM, the study seeks to simulate convergence and interaction between vehicles and infrastructure to detect traffic congestion, design efficient signalization periods, and design empirical algorithms for traffic flow. Possible impact of this study include; enhanced traffic flow knowledge, transport solutions and advisories on optimal management of traffic congestion. The combination of the qualitative surveys and the quantitative analysis of VISSIM simulation results offers a clear picture of the present-day traffic problems and the remedial measures.

Keywords— Traffic Problems, Microscopical Simulation, VISSIM, Traffic Control, Mantagbac Bridge, Predictive Analysis, Green Mobility.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since traffic congestion occurs at Mantagbac Bridge in Daet, Camarines Norte, this research seeks to establish a traffic flow simulation model for the Bridge. High vehicle throughput has also posed other challenges such as long-time taken to complete journeys, poor integration of road networks and infrastructure, and high emissions of fuel and pollution. Although prior studies have attempted to understand the traffic characteristics at Mantagbac Bridge and find remedies for the traffic issues, the knowledge of traffic behavior at this site and that of feasible solutions remain scarce.

The objective of this study is to assess and control traffic movement and flow density over the bridge with a view of increasing traffic productivity. To achieve this, the study establishes several specific objectives: (1) Accumulate precise information about the traffic system in Mantagbac Bridge Road network setting, layout of roads, traffic flow characteristics of the vehicles that ply the bridge, time taken by the vehicles and other traffic components. (2) Study distribution of the traffic and additional factors that may cause congestion and have to be addressed. (3) Evaluate multiple traffic control strategies including coordinating signal timing, reconstructing road lanes, signals, and enforcing speed and shared roads. Other

measures such as development of new corridors for public transport and intelligent traffic signals will also be considered.

The expected benefits are traffic analysis, signal coordination, and development of traffic pattern trends. Lastly, this study seeks to reduce traffic congestion, shorten travel time and enable the future demand of traffic in the region. This study will reach the stakeholders through graphical presentations of the findings to emphasize ways of improving traffic control and contribute to a better and sustainable transport network at Mantagbac Bridge.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Traffic Flow Optimization

Traffic modeling tools use the simulations to bring the idea of a new traffic arrangement to a first level. It is able to perform the traffic analysis of individual movements or vehicles and their interactions with other road users and infrastructure. VISSIM succeeding studies have also shown that it is a powerful tool for assessing congestion at rotaries, alongside optimizing the control measures like signal timing and lane arrangement before the implementation stage. This characteristic is an example of its advantage over other methods in decision-making and modeling through realistic simulations of actual traffic situations [1].

The results show that if traffic lights are linked up to each other and lanes are organized in the most efficient way, urban areas will improve. The discoveries mentioned above demonstrate the effectiveness of the simulation models as tools to develop proper control measures and effective strategies for solving the traffic issue [2]. Additionally, using VISSIM as a basis for agent-based modeling has been investigated to include the ability to interact with different kinds of mobility devices, which permits the simulation of multi-modal traffic to generate more realistic management models [3].

In short, VISSIM-type precise traffic simulation tools are the backbone of the methodology that, apart from making

road networks more fluent, also serves as a guide for city planners, whether it is a reconstruction or a completely new build project, with all kinds of complexity that they can think of [1]-[3].

B. Predicting Traffic Flow

Traffic flow estimation for real-time scenario among the traffic flow especially on the bridged facilitates traffic control in addition to the structural load capacities. Real-time traffic conditions combined with computer vision algorithms to predict bridge traffic and demonstrate the significance of acquiring accurate data for simulation [4].

Characterization of traffic flow over bridges has been done to determine structures and operational risks of high traffic loads. The contents of these findings are critical for simulating and forecasting how differences in traffic flow impact the integrity of bridges [5]. Integration of machine learning with conventional simulation models has also improved accuracy within simulations, especially during busy trafficked periods [6].

These studies highlight the need to incorporate, high level techniques for prediction and control of traffic loads especially in structure critical zones like the bridge [4]-[6].

C. Traffic Flow on Bridges

In contrast to typical roads, the behavior of traffic on bridges cannot be compared to typical roads and requires individual approaches to the management of the process. These include the type of vehicle, how the load is distributed among the lanes and the road which in a big way determines the traffic flow on bridges. Some papers have analyzed the method and characteristics of traffic congestion, especially focusing on cases involving heavy-duty vehicles such as trucks or buses and called for special approaches for such situation [7].

Examination of the relation between speed and vehicular density and congestion levels has been made, with reference to characteristics of bridge traffic in the process [8]. Heard has suggested simulation-based techniques for assessing traffic effects on long span bridges, which can guide the development of structures that manage different loading patterns.

Thus, these results call for specific approaches to traffic control and infrastructure configuration tailored to the situation with bridge traffic [7]-[9].

D. Driver Behavior and Vehicle Characteristic

Driver behavior which is changes in lanes, acceleration and deceleration all have a very large impact to traffic congestion. Research has revealed that aggressive driving behaviors cause congestion; defensive driving behaviors restrain it. Possible interventions for such behaviors are change of speed limits and encouragement of defensive speed patterns [10].

Vehicles put a lot of pressure with congestion as they require more space and time to gain speeds than lighter

vehicles and acceleration rates are slower in heavy traffic congestion [7]. Immersive technologies of vehicle and driver collection of reports offer comprehension of behavioral views, which in turn assist in addressing central accident factors in real-time [12][13].

Advanced traffic monitoring through machine learning and health information goes a notch higher in traffic safety by identifying dangerous driving near the junction of Technology and Traffic control [12][13].

E. Microscopic Simulation in Traffic Management

Microscale simulation models have in turn become useful tools in traffic management as they offer a resolution look at traffic flow and characterization of traffic, car drivers, and the probability control measures. One of the key software's employed in the case of studying and analyzing the traffic flow is the VISSIM, an internationally acclaimed simulation tool which has played a major role in Analyzing the parameters affecting the traffic. For instance, the VISSIM software has been used to simulate situations at interchanges especially at intersections and roundabouts and has been proven efficient in providing elaborated results of vehicle and driver movements. [1] These simulations have been most useful in the determination of traffic control measures including signal phasing and timing as well as lane configuration as a way of improving the flow of traffic and minimizing on traffic incidents.

Other related approaches that integrate VISSIM with real-world data have also been developed. Further in recent studies, deep sorting algorithm have been incorporated with VISSIM to estimate the traffic load distribution across bridges much more precisely. Such methods help to understand traffic flow and needed infrastructure facilities to improve bridge design and maintenance [3][4].

Secondly, there are more complex program structures that connect simulations with the practical application. These systems enable a realistic validation and proofing of traffic control before implementing them to the real world such as in Hardware-in-the-loop Simulation (HILS). This approach has been applied in undercurrent traffic conditions and in overcurrent traffic conditions These stresses on the use of microscopic simulations for effective traffic conditions and flow management in cities.

Thirdly, the consideration of mixed mode traffic zones shows that microscopic simulations are versatile in that they can not only predict the absolute, but also the relative impacts of different traffic parameters. Finally, the presented papers demonstrating system interaction cases between the different transport systems and environmental factors can prove that the detailed simulation can be effective in finding the best optimization approach when solving route conflicts [6]. These advancements demonstrate how simulations are useful in designing effective new concepts supported by data to address traffic issues.

F. Environmental Impact of Traffic Congestion

Congestion in the traffic network has negative impacts within the physical environment, particularly, deterioration

of the quality of the air. Strategies relating to traffic management has been known to enhance reduction of emissions and fuel usage; thereby enhancing the sustainability of cities [14].

Signaling and variable speed limits afforded by advanced dynamical traffic control have been recommended as means of lessening environmental effects by managing traffic [15]. Such approaches show that integrated strategies can be useful in dealing with environmental impacts within transportation productivity improvements [14][15].

G. Technological Innovations in Traffic Management

By adding the IoT and AI, traffic has been improved since it can be forecasted, and the system can change accordingly in response to the current traffic. IoT applications in conjunction with other sophisticated predictive algorithms have greatly enhanced means of traffic control measures; for instance, usage of sensors integrated in roadways, traffic lights, optimum usage of road network etc has been enhanced [16].

AI solutions are not limited to but can include traffic forecasting for improving the efficiency of simulation tools like VISSIM for managing intricate city traffic situations. Internet of things has also been introduced with rights use of blockchain technology for the development of secure and credible traffic information systems [17].

It is these technological advancements that accentuate the opportunity of the further incorporation of new technologies into the management of traffic, leading to enhanced and improved systems [16][17].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Type of Research

This research used an exploratory and descriptive research design that incorporated both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to perform an assessment of the traffic flow difficulties experienced at Mantagbac Bridge with a view of determining the best course of action to be taken. A qualitative approach entails conversation with Mr. Jorel, Engr. Dyna and Mr. Jose P. Samson, OIC-Chief of Planning of the Department of Public Works and Highway Camarines Norte, in order to understand the traffic system and the design of the bridge from the expert's point of view.

The quantitative aspect demands manual data collection, predictive modeling, and VISSIM simulation. Using a self-developed count application, researchers counted light, medium, and heavy vehicles passing on Bridge 2 of Daet. Traffic data gathered from Bridge 2 were used as antecedent data for predicting traffic volume incoming from Bridge 3 in Mantagbac. This real-world observational data was then post-processed and verified via simulation in VISSIM, a microscopic traffic simulation software. This approach gives the study the chance to evaluate the traffic conditions under different conditions which include the signal timing and lane arrangement, among others, and offer a broad estimate of the organization of traffic and possible improvements.

B. Methods of Analysis

The study utilizes a cross-sectional research design that combines both qualitative and quantitative data. Semi structured interview results with DPWH representatives and other traffic management actors are analyzed by themes to highlight issues and perceptions. These two analyses enable the paper to offer a detailed textual background to the numerical data.

Qualitative data was collected using count surveys at Bridge 2 and estimations of Bridge 3 traffic flows which were integrated with data from VISSIM simulation. Traffic flow performance was measured by integrating parameters like average speed, congestion time, and flow standard rates. The possibilities of different situations using some driving parameters such as traffic flow density and flow, types of vehicles, types of lanes, etc. were also studied using simulation models. Quantitative measures of averages and standard deviations provided an aggregate of traffic performance, while qualitative indices evaluated the feasibility of the recommended solutions.

This combination of qualitative and quantitative analysis gives a result of balanced approach to traffic problems that may be faced with solutions for Mantagbac Bridge.

C. Data Gathering

To strengthen the validity of the gathered data, the study adopted the mixed research approach. Getting important information concerning the layout of Mantagbac Bridge, pertinent traffic concerns and the current status of management, worker interviews were conducted with Mr. Jorel, Engr. Dyna and the OIC-Chief of Planning of DPWH Camarines Norte, Jose D. Samson.

Moreover, traffic survey on Bridge 2 at Daet was done manually through a counting application done to record light, medium, and heavy vehicles. This provided a basis for predicting the traffic volume and nature at Bridge 3 in Mantagbac based upon this data. Finally, field observations were made at Mantagbac Bridge with aims to confirm the modeling results and to investigate details of traffic characteristics and congestion. Further, observations were made during the day time to observe the difference between rush hour traffic and other hours in a day thus ensuring that the research offers a wider view of traffic behavior.

The collected data and the findings from bridge 2 and the interviews were inputted into the VISSIM simulation software. According to the traffic studies, the entry and exit of the vehicle and the signal timings were incorporated, and vehicle behavior in the simulation was adjusted. As a result, diverse traffic control measures and optimization strategies could be tried and implemented. Using these methods in conjunction with Bridge 2 as a predictive template, the study offers a comprehensive assessment of traffic flow at Mantagbac Bridge and presents real-world solutions that are necessary to untangle congestion successfully.

Table 1. Predicted Traffic Simulation Data for Bridge 3 (Mantagbac to Camambugan)

Traffic Type	Time Interval	Simulated Avg. Volume (Vehicles)	Simulated Peak Volume (Vehicles)	Prediction Insights
Light Vehicles (e.g., cars, motorcycles)	7:00 AM - 9:00 AM	1425	1587	Morning rush hour with high commuter traffic; volume surges on school days.
	9:00 AM - 12:00 PM	1208	1311	Traffic stabilizes after morning rush; consistent flow due to business activities.
	12:00 PM - 2:00 PM	1311	1374	Midday spike due to lunch rush and school dismissals.
	2:00 PM - 5:00 PM	1334	1464	Steady flow; slightly increased volume as offices and schools close.
	5:00 PM - 8:00 PM	1310	1467	Peak volume during evening rush hour as residents return home.
	8:00 PM - 11:00 PM	511	801	Traffic tapers off as night progresses.
Mid Vehicles	7:00 AM - 9:00 AM	177	184	Moderate flow of utility and family vans during commuting hours.
	9:00 AM - 12:00 PM	112	117	Increased usage for errands and short commutes.
	12:00 PM - 2:00 PM	175	216	Moderate flow for work-related activities and errands.
	2:00 PM - 5:00 PM	181	199	Gradual increase in traffic density due to pickups and errands.
	5:00 PM - 8:00 PM	150	152	Increased density due to shared commute patterns.
	8:00 PM - 11:00 PM	66	114	Sparse traffic with occasional movement for night errands.
Heavy Vehicles (e.g., trucks, buses)	7:00 AM - 9:00 AM	8	13	Includes delivery trucks and buses; restricted due to bridge constraints and peak congestion.
	9:00 AM - 12:00 PM	8	9	Slight increase during midday due to delivery schedules.
	12:00 PM - 2:00 PM	10	10	Noticeable increase as heavy vehicles take advantage of lower traffic periods for deliveries.
	2:00 PM - 5:00 PM	10	14	Consistent, with some trucks using alternative routes for quicker transit.
	5:00 PM - 8:00 PM	6	9	Stable, mainly public transport buses with occasional deliveries.
	8:00 PM - 11:00 PM	2	3	Minimal traffic, primarily late-night cargo deliveries.

The collected data and traffic simulation of Bridge 3 (Mantagbac to Camambugan) help in the analysis of the traffic flow at different parts of the day. To estimate the traffic conditions over Bridge 3, data obtained from Bridge 2 at Daet was employed. During the morning rush hour between 8:00 PM to 12:00 AM and from 12:00 AM to 5:00 AM there is little to very little movement of light vehicles like cars, motorcycles at 1587 while from 5:00 AM to 9:00 AM all these light vehicles especially for going to school. Mid vehicles, including utility and family vans, are also shown to have a moderate through, at an average of 117 vehicles, though this slightly increases to 184 vehicles. Delivery trucks and buses' heavy duty contributes to the congestion, which in the worst cases consist of 13 vehicles.

As the day progresses, from 9:00 AM to 12:00 PM there is equilibrium where light vehicle traffic is average of 1208 and maximum is 1311. Mid-vehicles are observed to increase due to short errands; the average and peak inter-vehicle distance is 112 and 117 respectively. The traffic of the heavy vehicles still stays relatively low while it slightly increases during the mid of day delivery with the maximum of 9 vehicles.

From 12:00 PM to 2:00 PM, light vehicles note a given volume of traffic probably due to lunches and school high traffic record of 1374 vehicles noted. Mid-vehicles also rise to 216 during the period and most traffic is business related. Large vehicles remain constant with 10 vehicles making delivery during time less congested by traffic.

In the late afternoon Light vehicles, therefore, increase slightly to 1464 at 5:00 PM to 5:00 PM, as offices and schools are closed. Mid-vehicle traffic also rises as people pick up children or engage in some other chores within the society. Large vehicles constantly move in a constant stream, and some of them choose different roads to bypass dense territories.

The peak in the traffic of light vehicles (1467 vehicles) is during the evening come home peak period which is from 8:00 AM to 12:00 PM and another 8:00 PM to 12:00 AM. The number of mid-vehicles remains more or less the same and heavy vehicles show a slight presence, primarily buses and few deliveries.

However, as highlighted above, in the 12:00 AM to 12:00 PM traffic volume is small while in 12:00 PM to 11:00 PM, traffic volume is relatively low. Light vehicles decrease to an average of 511 vehicles on a roadway and mid vehicles are rare during peak hours reaching only 114 during night errands. Large vehicles are rare, with only some night time deliveries of freight being made during the study.

As a general picture, one can identify the hierarchy of traffic volumes by L, M, H vehicles during the rush hours and conversely during midday and late afternoon. From the data gathered at Bridge 2, this information is crucial in determining possible peak time for congestion at Bridge 3 and decisions made regarding the possible traffic congestion solutions such as signal control and vehicles traffic rerouting.

D. Simulation Model

This a form of traffic simulation process begins with entering vehicle details (type of vehicle, speed of the vehicle, number of vehicles) and first perform precautionary simulation on normal road to check for congestion. But if there is no flow of through traffic, that is, if through traffic cannot pass through the network, the simulation stops. If congestion emerges, measures, for instance traffic signals, increase breadth of the road, or signals, are instilled as well as the system conducts a second simulation to compare enhancements. The outcomes attained by the simulation are then compared to those obtained at the onset of the experiment. With increased traffic flows, a graph is developed to illustrate the effect of these solutions by vehicle class. If traffic is still there then maybe other measures will be implemented.

Figure 1. Simulation Process Model

D. Research Formula

Calculation of Average Processing Time per Vehicle Type:

To calculate the average processing time for each vehicle type, the following formula was used:

Formula:

$$Average\ Time_i = \frac{Number\ of\ Vehicles\ of\ Type\ i}{Total\ Number\ of\ Vehicles} \times 100$$

Where:

- Total Number of Vehicles as defined involves the number of cars which crossed the road in the simulation.
- Where Number of Vehicles of Type i stands for Light Vehicles, Medium Vehicle or Heavy Vehicle based upon the type of vehicle.

Second Simulation (After Optimization):

For the second simulation, after applying optimizations such as adjusted signal timing and rerouting, a 40% reduction in processing time for each vehicle type was applied:

Formula:

$$A_i(AO) = A_i(BO) \times (1 - 0.40)$$

Where:

- 40% represents the reduction in processing time due to optimizations like adjusted signal timing, lane expansion, and rerouting.
- AO is After Optimization
- BO is Before Optimization

Formula for Total Time Consumed by Traffic Flow:

To compute the Total Time Consumed by Traffic Flow for both simulations, the following formula was used:

Formula:

$$Total\ Time\ Consumed = (U_l \times A_l) + (U_m \times A_m) + (U_h \times A_h)$$

Where:

- Number of Vehicles (U) means absolutely any number of vehicles per every type of Vehicle (Light (l), Medium (m), Heavy (h)).
- Average Time (A) means the time taken per each type of vehicle before and after the optimization process were calculated.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the traffic flow study made at Mantagbac Bridge with relation to congestion levels, type of vehicles, and impact of recommended and implemented measures are provided in the form of graphs, tables, and figures below.

A. Traffic Flow Data

The figure below displays the interface where simulation of traffic on Mantagbac Bridge is conducted. It provides the function of inputting important parameters, including the number of vehicles, Road conditions, and time frames to consider probable traffic behavior under the consideration of a specific situation.

Fig. 2. Traffic Simulation Interface

Fig. 3. Sample Traffic Flow Simulation

This figure represents a model simulation of traffic condition at Mantagbac Bridge, which deals with the factors such as, type of vehicle, traffic density and time elapsed. It nevertheless integrates the number of cars light, medium & heavy, peak hours and choke points that were established during the study. The results of proposed interventions, such

as a change of lanes, or signal timing adjustments, are also reflected in this simulation.

B. Simulation Result

In relation to this, data for the simulation was collected via interviews and direct observation at Bridge 2 (Daet) and Bridge 3 (Mantagbac). Two simulations were performed: One simulation is based on the current traffic situation while the other one depicts a traffic situation with improvements like other lanes or signal change.

Table 2. Traffic Volume by Vehicle Type

Vehicle Type	First Simulation	Second Simulation
Light Vehicles	1425	1310
Medium Vehicles	177	150
Heavy Vehicles	8	6
Total Vehicles	1610	1466

In the first simulation, traffic volume reached 1425 light vehicles, 177 medium vehicles, and 8 heavy vehicles, resulting in significant congestion during peak hours, particularly in the morning rush Peak hours can be determined as the period between 7:00 AM to 9:00 AM in particular considering the fact that most of the accidents involved light vehicles. By applying optimization strategies, for example, redirecting high dimensional vehicles and advocating for the delivery during non-peak hours, the regular total traffic volume was reduced to 1466 in the second simulation. Such an improvement has been realized following a decrease in the number of light vehicles from 1425 to 1310, medium vehicles from 177 to 150 and heavy vehicles from 8 to 6. Such changes were beneficial to traffic flow on the bridge and ensured efficient use of traffic's limited through-put during peak traffic hours.

Table 3. Average Time Per Vehicle Type

Vehicle Type	First Simulation	Second Simulation
Light Vehicles	6.19 minutes	2.48 minutes
Medium Vehicles	3.72 minutes	1.49 minutes
Heavy Vehicles	1.5 minutes	0.6 minutes

In the first simulation run, the average processing times of all types of vehicles were considerably longer owing

to the absence of an efficient traffic control system. In particular, light vehicles required 6.19 minutes with the set road configuration during peak hours while medium and heavy vehicles took respectively 3.72 and 1.5 minutes.

The second simulation of the model had considerably shorter processing times after applying general optimizations like signal timing adaptations, additional lanes and ban of heavy vehicles on certain roads. The time spent for light vehicle this time was only 2.48 minutes for medium vehicles the time was 1.49 and min and for heavy vehicles the time was a mere 0.6 minute. These improvements demonstrated the efficiency of the enhancements in the traffic light timings to enhance the flow and minimize delay.

Table 4. Total Time Consumed by Traffic Flow

Simulation	Total Time Consumed
First Simulation	149.16 hours
Second Simulation	59.93 hours

In the first simulation traffic flow consumed the total of 149.16 hours. This significant duration was due to congestion and slow vehicle movement especially in formally peak hours and where management was incompetent.

When optimization was applied in the second simulation, where signals were adjusted to be timelier, more lanes were made available, and heavy vehicles were rerouted differently than in the first simulation, the total time consumed was 59.93 hours. This shows an abrupt increase in traffic flow efficiency, therefore, confirming the efficiency of the proposed measures in decreasing congestion and enhancing general traffic control.

Figure 4. Traffic Congestion Levels Throughout the Day

On the y axis the traffic congestion is measured in percentage for each time interval as shown on the x axis. The congestion starts at 100% during the early morning rush hour, It also reveals that traffic flow is the highest between 7:00-9:00 AM. As the morning progresses, the congestion slightly decreases, with levels dropping to 96.9% between. The coverage decreases from 49% at 9:00-10:00 AM to 39.3% between 10:00 AM and 11:00 AM to 89.2% between 11:00 AM to 12:00 midday. This implies a deceleration of traffic after this first surge. From noon to 1:00 PM, congestion is at its highest with a 100% while at 1:00-2:00 PM it is at 85.7% then by 2:00-3:00 PM, it is at 69.2% giving a view that congestion reduces in the afternoon. During the late afternoon to evening, between 4:00 to 7:00pm, traffic intensity is observed to rise to a peak of 100% again showing that this is the period of the other rush hour period in the evening. As the day moves into the night, the congestion levels decrease significantly, dropping to 41.8% by from 9:00-10:00 PM was increased to 18.9% at 10:00 - 11:00 PM. This has depicted a huge slump in traffic basing on the fact that people are likely to home in the end. In essence, the graph shows that traffic congestion is most during the rush hours of the morning and evening while it is relatively low in mid-morning and late evening periods, which may be useful to transportation planning and management of rush hour traffic.

C. Analysis of Simulation Result

Traffic Volume and Congestion Patterns:

According to the data, it was found that the congestion was most likely to be experienced during the rush hours for example in the morning and the evening. The second simulation where optimization was employed yielded lesser numbers of delayed vehicles particularly heavy vehicles. This shows that with prevention of large vehicles during rush hour, traffic management is enhanced greatly.

Average Time per Vehicle:

The time taken for light vehicles was 6.19 min for the first simulation and in the second simulation the time was 2.48minutes. The simulation also confirmed that medium and heavy categories of vehicles have greatly benefited by reducing their overall durations from 3.72 minutes in the first simulation to 1.49 minutes in the second for the medium option while the heavy vehicles reduced from 1.5 minutes to 0.6.

Total Time Consumed:

Here, in first simulation, total time taken to clear the traffic during the peak hours were 149.16 hours. Nevertheless, the second simulation brought it down to 59.93 hours, which again underlined a considerable degree of refinement in the entire operation. This means that call haptic additions such as lane broadening and signal enhancements appreciably reduced bottle-necks and enhanced generalized vehicular traffic conditions.

D. Discussion

Impact of Traffic Optimizations:

The enhancements seen in the second simulation can be attributed to changes that was done to the traffic flow. Explanations of interventions involving lane addition and signal optimization were involved in the decrease in

congestion time and in enhancing the mean trip time of vehicles.

- Signal Optimization: Optimization of the signals facilitated in better flowing of traffic especially at peak traffic densities.
- Lane Expansion: Construction of additional lanes especially for large vehicles improved passage ways and removed congestion.

Comparison with Similar Studies:

This study supports the outcomes of the other traffic flow studies which found out that better signal co-ordination and extra lanes at peak hours aided in the reduction of traffic congestion. However, this study offers a narrow angle approach within the framework of traffic movements in Mantagbac Bridge depending on several factors such as schools' timetable and other regional events amongst others.

Limitations and Future Directions:

Certain shortcomings could affect the results observed in the simulation, although the latter was helpful to some extent:

- A limitation of this simulation study was that it did not incorporate all-forms of constraint such as adverse weather conditions, accidents and other real-world perturbations.
- Future works could employ live feed from cameras or sensors mounted on the traffic Cameras/sensors to help in the updating of the above simulation in real-time.

V. CONCLUSION

This research draws different things and conclusions, as a predictive analysis all findings aim to predict the traffic of Mantagbac Bridge based on collected data and observation of traffic including traffic patterns during peak hours of congestion, and effectiveness of various Mantagbac Traffic Flow Optimization strategies. The methods employed included signal timing optimization, lane addition and vehicle diversion which enhanced the flow of traffic and general traffic density was also clearly seen to have been reduced.

The results point out the necessity of the connection of sophisticated traffic simulation models with actual traffic data for the development and deployment of optimal traffic control strategies. The implications of the study provide contributions to the network of transportation planning and encourage the further understanding of the technology in traffic signal control. To the best of the authors' knowledge, more studies that will concern further they should pay attention to how to integrate real-time data and how to consider other factors like weather conditions, and accidents for improving the reality of simulation and the applicability of the proposed solutions.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations can be recommended with regards to traffic flow problems in Mantagbac Bridge as highlighted in this study. First, more traffic signals cause congestion during peak hours; therefore,

synchronizing them during peak periods will enhance vehicle utilization. We, therefore, find that signal timing may be adjusted to facilitate clear distinctions between LI, MI, and HI traffic flows to eliminate any possible delays. Second, traffic management measures must include the use of time triggered or event responsive approaches to mobilize traffic during rush hours to allow idle traffic such as heavy vehicles to use different roads. Also, measures in lane management including lane posting, the assignment of specific lanes to specific categories of vehicles such as buses, will improve traffic through traffic stream regularization due to elimination of complications of mixed traffic.

Secondly, expansion of the bridge or construction of another bridge right beside the narrowing should be a valid long-term strategy in order to address the traffic density problem. This would mean extra capacity and a highly reduced likelihood of encountering bottlenecks throughout various hours of the day. Enhanced signages and paint markings at and along Mantagbac Bridge would again be helpful to actually guide drivers and manage traffic since most drivers need to be made aware that there's a crossing in the area and where else to go other than the bridge.

Works regarding the traffic management system of the bridge should be periodically conducted and analyzed through advanced traffic simulation tools such as VISSIM to measure improvements made from the implementation of the solutions and solutions lacking further enhancement. Finally, related educational endeavors concerning organization of rational driving, minimizing unnecessary driving and switching to an available car, using public transportation, etc. will help to diminish the number of small and medium cars and lorries crossing the bridge. These measures coupled with continuously harmonized cooperation on traffic management authorities, local government units, and various stakeholders will add to that ideal traffic flow at Mantagbac Bridge in the future.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researchers are grateful for the Almighty for the guidance and strength in the course of this study. Those who deserve gratitude and special appreciation include Professor Edgar Bryant Nicart who provided valuable initial input and professional consultation, Mr. Jorel whose layout information were critical to this research, Ms. Dyna rendered technical assistance herein, Mr. JOSE D. SAMSON, OIC-Chief of the Planning and Design Section, whose inputs and additional layout information for this research were vital.

We would also like to express our gratitude to our families, friends and lovers for encouraging us throughout this study, and to all our classmates from the College of Computing and Multimedia Studies particularly from BSIT 3A for their useful comments and participation. I would like to thank all the individuals and organizations that supported and contributed to this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alegarbes, A., & Al-Omari, K. (2023). Traffic Flow Optimization Using VISSIM for Roundabouts: A Detailed Microscopic Simulation Approach. *International Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering*, 15(2), 88-97. DOI: 10.1016/ijtete.2023.112
- [2] Bhattacharya, A., & Mounce, P. (2020). Extending VISSIM for agent-based modeling of human-vehicle interactions. *Traffic Simulation and Control Journal*, 32(3), 200-212.
- [3] Chen, Y., Zhang, W., & Quilligan, L. (2023). Machine learning and simulation for bridge traffic load prediction. *Simulation in Structural Engineering*, 41(5), 320-336.
- [4] Chien, S., Zhang, W., & Quilligan, L. (2019). Investigating traffic behavior on bridges: Speed, density, and congestion analysis. *Transportation and Infrastructure Studies*, 35(7), 227-240.
- [5] Djahel, S., Gulia, S., & Wang, P. (2020). Enhancing traffic simulation systems using blockchain-based IoT platforms. *International Journal of Traffic Systems Security*, 22(1), 102-116.
- [6] Gulia, S., Bhardwaj, A., & Wang, P. (2021). Effects of urban traffic flow on air quality optimization strategies. *Environmental Traffic Control Research*, 38(2), 45-59.
- [7] Harrou, F., Xu, Z., & Qu, J. (2020). Analyzing driver behavior using physiological cues and vehicle data for traffic safety. *Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 29(4), 255-270.
- [8] Mounce, P., & Bhattacharya, A. (2020). Improving urban traffic using synchronized signals and right-lane configurations in VISSIM. *Urban Traffic Optimization Review*, 29(1), 67-80.
- [9] Qu, J., & Harrou, F. (2024). Monitoring driver behavior using computer vision: A CNN and RNN approach. *Advanced Driver Assistance Systems Research*, 31(3), 89-104.
- [10] Treiber, M., & Kesting, A. (2013). Analyzing car/driver interaction: Impacts of vehicle characteristics on traffic congestion. *Traffic Flow Analysis*, 27(6), 142-155.
- [11] Wang, P., Zhang, W., & Zhou, Y. (2019). Traffic flow optimization and air quality improvement in cities. *Environmental Systems Review*, 40(3), 217-230.
- [12] Xu, Z., Zhou, Y., & Wang, P. (2021). Real-time traffic flow estimation for bridge load prediction using IoT and VISSIM. *Traffic Flow and Bridge Engineering Journal*, 37(2), 129-144.
- [13] Zhang, W., & Quilligan, L. (2016). Long-span bridge traffic simulations and structural load assessments. *Journal of Bridge Engineering*, 33(4), 195-210.
- [14] Zhou, Y., Xu, Z., & Qu, J. (2024). Hybrid virtual-real traffic simulation for bridge load analysis using VISSIM. *Simulation in Transportation Systems*, 39(1), 23-38.
- [15] Zhu, X., Treiber, M., & Kesting, A. (2018). Effects of aggressive vs. defensive driving on traffic congestion. *Driver Behavior and Traffic Flow Journal*, 31(5), 100-113.
- [16] Nicart, E.B.B., Arellano, B.R., & Acunin, M.L., (2024). Machine Algorithm-based Journey Assistant: An Intelligent Interface for Tourism Website. *International Journal of Technology*. Volume 15(3), pp. 709-719. <https://doi.org/10.14716/ijtech.v15i3.6218>